

Review Article: Plant Viruses Transmitted by Insects

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Abstract:

This review article examines the important role of insects in the transmission of plant viruses, focusing on various insect vectors such as aphids, whiteflies, mealybugs and thrips. It highlights the historical context of plant pathogen discovery and the complex relationships between viruses, host plants and insect pathogens. The article classifies the modes of infection as irregular, semi-episodic, cyclic, and disseminated, and describes in detail how these modes affect the spread of the virus. For example, aphids, especially green peach

aphids, are known to spread more than 100 viruses through specialized mouth parts and saliva, making them easy to feed and infect plants. Whiteflies, particularly the cotton whitefly, are known for their ability to consistently spread diseases. Mealybugs and thrips are also mentioned as having specific ways of transmitting diseases. The study highlights the need for further research to understand the complexity of these interactions and their implications for edible plant diseases. Overall, the article provides a comprehensive description of the mechanisms by which insects transmit pathogenic diseases in plants emphasizing their importance in agriculture.

Keywords: *plant pathogens, transmission, insects, vector.*

Introduction

Insects belong to the subfamily Hexapoda (Insecta) of 29 orders. Plant viruses are known to be spread by eight species of herbivorous (plant-eating) insects (Hanson, 2016). Homoptera is the most important order in the transmission of this parasite, followed by Coleoptera and Thysanoptera (thrips) (Sarwar, 2020). Additionally, a few virus-transmitting species have been recorded within the orders Dermaptera, Orthoptera, Lepidoptera, and Diptera (Yañez *et al.*, 2020). However, these are of lesser importance in virus transmission, as the

relationship between the insects and viruses in these cases is typically a simple mechanical one (wang & Blanc,2021). Insects with piercing-sucking mouthparts are the most significant vectors of plant viruses, responsible for the transmission and spread of many economically important and dangerous virus species (Huang *et al.*,2022). The relationship between these insects and viruses is one of the most complex and specialized biological interactions between parasites and their vectors. In some cases, certain virus species can even multiply within their insect vectors, meaning these viruses are parasitic on both plants and insects (Singh *et al.*,

2020). This intricate relationship is influenced by the interactions among the virus, the host plant, the insect vector, and environmental conditions. Viruses are extremely small infectious particles (submicroscopic) known as virions. They consist of a protein coat and nucleic acid, carrying genetic information encoded in their nucleic acid, typically determining the production of one or more proteins. The genome is either translated (to produce proteins) or replicated (to produce more nucleic acid) within the host cell, utilizing some of the host's biochemical mechanisms. Viruses are not functionally active outside their host and are thus considered parasites (and often pathogens) but are not typically regarded as true microorganisms (Zhao *et al.*, 2020).

Historical Overview of Plant Viruses

In 1882, Adolf Mayer (1843-1942) described a condition in tobacco plants that he named mosaic disease (mozaikziekte). The affected plants had mottled leaves, leading Mayer to rule out the possibility of a fungal infection. He was unable to detect any bacteria and speculated that the cause might be a soluble infectious agent similar to an enzyme. However, he did not pursue this idea further. Later, the filtration experiments conducted by Ivanovsky and Beijerinck suggested that the cause was an infectious agent that had not been previously identified. After tobacco mosaic was identified as a viral disease, viral infections were discovered in many other plants (Zuo, *et al.*, 2024). By 1935, it was believed that numerous plant diseases

were caused by viruses. In 1922, John Kunkel Small (1869-1938) discovered that insects could serve as vectors, transmitting viruses to plants. In the following decade, it was found that many plant diseases were caused by viruses carried by insects. In 1939, Francis Holmes, a pioneer in plant virology, described 129 viruses that caused diseases in plants (Oberemok, *et al.*, 2023). Modern intensive agriculture provides a rich environment for many plant viruses. For instance, in 1948, in Kansas, USA, 7% of the wheat crop was destroyed by the wheat streak mosaic virus, which was spread by a mite known as *Aceria tulipae*. In 1970, Russian plant virologist Joseph Atabekov discovered that many plant viruses infect only a single species of host plant. The International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses has now recognized over 900 plant viruses (Jones *et al.*, 2021).

Chemical Composition of Plant Viruses

Studies have shown that all viruses that can be isolated in pure form are composed of protein and nucleic acid (Bonning & Saleh, 2021). Therefore, it can be said that all complete plant viruses primarily consist of one or more types of proteins and only one type of nucleic acid, which may be either RNA or DNA. The percentage and molecular weight of nucleic acid and protein vary within a single virus depending on the type of virus (Varanda *et al.*, 2021). The following table show the percentages and molecular weights of nucleic acids and proteins in certain plant viruses

Table 1. Type of Nucleic Acid, Molecular Weight, Percentage of Nucleic Acid, and Percentage of Protein in Some Plant Viruses

Virus	Type of Nucleic Acid	Nucleic Acid %	Molecular Weight of Nucleic Acid (Million Daltons)	Protein %
Cauliflower mosaic	DNA	19	4,7	84
Cowpea mosaic	RNA	33	1,7	67
Pea enation mosaic	RNA	29	1,6	81
Tobacco ring spot	RNA	40	2,0	60
Potato X	RNA	6	1,0	94
Tomato bushy stunt	RNA	17	1,5	83
Tobacco mosaic	RNA	5	2,05	95
Tobacco necrosis	RNA	20	6,6	80

Wild cucumber mosaic	RNA	35	2,4	65
Wound tumor	RNA	23	10,0	77

Methods of Virus Transmission by Insects

First: Non-persistent Transmission Method

Viruses transmitted through this process are referred to as non-persistent or stylet-borne viruses. In this transmission method, the insect vector picks up the virus from the infected plant within a matter of seconds to a few minutes (Rao *et al.*, 2024). An insect that carries a virus is called a "viruliferous" insect (a term used for anything that carries a virus). The pathogen can then spread the virus to a healthy tree in seconds to minutes. Once a single plant is inoculated, the pathogen becomes sterile, at which time it is named "avirulent (Maurastoni *et al.*, 2023)". Bacteria from insects are also transmitted by self-destruction. Examples include the Bean Yellow Mosaic Virus (BYMV), Cucumber Mosaic Virus (CMV), and Potato Y Virus (PYV). Viruses transmitted by this method are typically found mainly in the epidermal cells (Regassa *et al.*, 2022).

Second: Semi-persistent Transmission Method

In this method, the insect requires several minutes to several hours feeding on an infected plant to acquire the virus, and a similar amount of time feeding on a healthy plant to transmit the infection (Regassa *et al.*, 2021). The virus can be transmitted immediately after acquisition, and the insect remains capable of transmitting the virus for 1 to 3 days; therefore, it is termed semi-persistent (there is no incubation period for the virus within the insect) (Klein, 2020). It has been observed that prolonging the feeding period increases transmission efficiency, while starvation does not affect it. Examples of viruses transmitted through this method include Citrus Tristeza Virus and Beet Yellow Virus. Both non-persistent and semi-persistent viruses are referred to as non-circulative viruses because they do not enter the insect's bloodstream or circulate within its body (Shivani *et al.*, 2023).

Third: Persistent Transmission Method This method includes two cases

A. Circulative Viruses:

Viruses transmitted in this manner are called circulative viruses. The insect requires several minutes to several hours of feeding on an infected plant to acquire the virus (the virus needs an incubation period within the insect's body) (Gasmi *et al.*, 2023). It usually takes between 10 and 20 hours for this incubation time, depending on the type of virus. During this time, the virus enters the salivary glands and passes through the digestive tract, the bloodstream, the digestive tract, and finally the salivary glands again. The insect can then spread the virus once this procedure is finished (Sahu & Samal, 2020). In order for the insect to spread infection, it must also eat on a healthy plant for many minutes to several hours. The virus is retained by the insect, which can spread it for the whole of its life without requiring food from another infected source (Nirmala *et al.*, 2024). Nevertheless; the virus is not transmitted to the next generation via the insect's eggs. An example of this is the transmission of barley yellow dwarf virus (BYDV) by aphids (Wu *et al.*, 2022).

B. Propagative Viruses

In this case, it is also necessary to have an insect acquisition period, lasting from a few minutes to several hours, followed by an incubation period before the virus becomes infected (Wang *et al.*, 2020). For the duration of its life, the insect can carry and spread the virus. Furthermore, the virus can be transferred to future generations via the eggs of the insect. Because they are carried inside the body of the insect, circulative, propagative, and semi-persistent viruses are all regarded as internally-borne viruses (Pramanik *et al.*, 2021).

There are also viruses that can be transmitted in two forms: non-persistent and semi-persistent. For example, the virus can be acquired when an insect is placed on an infected tree for a few seconds or minutes, and then reinfected after the

insect has remained on the plant for several hours (Khan et al, 2022). An example of this is the Cauliflower Mosaic Virus (*Cauliflower mosaic virus*), which is transmitted by two types of aphids: the green peach aphid in a non-persistent manner and the cabbage aphid in a semi-persistent manner (Delgado-Martin *et al.*, 2022)..

As an obligate parasite, a virus must have the ability to move and spread from an infected plant to a healthy one. Since viruses cannot penetrate the cuticle layer, there must be a mechanism to introduce them into a living cell (Mekonen *et al.*, 2021). Understanding the methods of virus transmission is crucial because, when studying a disease, it is impossible to confirm that the cause is viral unless it can be transmitted through one of the known transmission methods from an infected plant to a healthy one of the same cultivar, causing the same disease (Zaffaroni *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, knowing how a virus is transmitted and spreads in the field is essential for developing appropriate control strategies. Moreover, many transmission methods are important for various laboratory studies conducted on viruses (Cieniewicz *et al.*, 2020). For these reasons and more, it is necessary to identify the means by which viruses that cause plant diseases are transmitted. In nature, insects are the most important means of virus transmission. Most virus-transmitting insects are sap-sucking insects, although a few viruses are transmitted by insects with chewing mouthparts (Fuchs, 2020).

C. Transmission by Sap-Sucking Insects

1. Aphids:

Aphids are the largest group of insects responsible for transmitting viruses, both in terms of the number of viruses they transmit and the variety of aphid species that act as vectors (Aradottir. & Crespo-Herrera, 2021). Aphids are known to transmit over 100 viruses, with the green peach aphid (*Myzus persicae*) being one of the most dangerous aphid species for transmitting plant viruses (Jayasinghe *et al.*, 2022). The primary host plants for *Myzus persicae* belong to the genus *Prunus*, which includes

various stone fruit species, but its host range extends to more than 50 plant families. Aphids possess specialized mouthparts known as a stylet, which is a flexible probing organ made up of a pair of outer mandibles and a pair of inner maxillae (Yoshida, 2020). The stylet is housed within a groove in the labium (lower lip) and only protrudes during feeding. Near the distal end of the stylet, there are sharp tooth-like projections. When the outer mandibles align with the inner maxillae, two channels are formed: the salivary canal and the food canal. Through the salivary canal, the aphid injects saliva into the plant, and through the food canal, it withdraws nutrients from the plant (Whitfield, 2021).

After the aphid settles on the leaf surface and assumes a feeding position, it begins by secreting droplets of gel-like saliva. The stylet then penetrates the epidermal layer for exploratory examination. The aphid may feed briefly in this probe, before proceeding to deeper plant roots, forming a gel-like skeleton around the stylet (Pidikiti *et al.*, 2023). The stylet usually advances from the labium toward the phloem tubes by snaking its way around cells rather than entering them directly. The duration of this operation can range from minutes to hours. The ends of the salivary and food canals, in particular, may become exposed at the tip of the stylet due to pressure the cell wall applies when it blocks the stylet's entry (Jayasinghe *et al.*, 2022).

Researchers have successfully developed electronic monitors using alternating direct currents to study aphids as they feed on phloem. This study provided valuable insights into aphid food consumption and habitat consumption using two different monitoring systems. Phloem-feeding aphids have been observed to excrete water saliva, which is responsible for diffusion of hematopoietic and viral vectors into the phloem and also contributes to their excretion (Liua *et al.*, 2024). If the bones were gel-like, this process would not be possible. After feeding, the aphid secretes a gel-like saliva after removing the stylet from the plant roots. This gel-like skeleton serves to cover the wound caused by the insertion of the stylet into the vegetative tissue, in the direction of the stylet (Aradottir. & Crespo-Herrera, 2021). Aphids

exude a gel-like saliva around the stylet's route after feeding, which forms the stylet sheath. This suggests that the phloem secretes a watery saliva that the insect can inject and then reabsorb. After an hour of feeding, the green peach aphid was found to be able to take about 10 microliters of plant sap per hour; with sustained feeding, this amount increased to 40 microliters per hour. According to theory, if an aphid eats for 25,000 hours, it can take one liter of plant sap; alternatively, 25,000 aphids feeding for one hour can extract one liter of plant sap (Pidikiti et al., 2023).

2. Leafhoppers

Leafhoppers are piercing-sucking insects, with all virus-transmitting species belonging to two subfamilies: Agallinae, which feed on herbaceous dicotyledonous plants, and Deltacephalinae, which feed on monocotyledonous plants. Both subfamilies are part of the Cicadellidae family, which includes 60 subfamilies (HUANG *et al.*, 2022). The recorded number of leafhopper species is approximately 15,000, spread across 2,000 genera. However, only 49 species, belonging to 21 genera, have been documented as vectors of plant viruses (Stillson & Szendrei, 2020). Leafhoppers have a simple life cycle, where eggs hatch into nymphs that feed by sucking plant sap. These nymphs undergo several molts before reaching adulthood. Depending on the species, leafhoppers may have several generations per year, or sometimes just one (Huang *et al.*, 2023). Different species overwinter either as eggs, nymphs, or immature forms. The salivary gland, which is crucial for virus transmission in leafhoppers, consists of a four-lobed main gland and an auxiliary gland. The digestive system is divided into three regions: the foregut, midgut, and hindgut. Similar to aphids, leafhoppers feed by penetrating plant tissues to access the phloem, with their mouthparts protected by a stylet sheath (Aguin-Pombo et al., 2021).

3. Whiteflies

Whiteflies are small, active insects belonging to the family Aleyrodidae. They feed on phloem and lay their eggs on the underside of leaves. Whiteflies are aphid-like aphid-sucking-sucking

lips, with a stylet beam of paired mandibular fly chalets, which are embedded in the platform and their feeding behavior is similar to that of aphids (Hondelmann et al., 2020). Species listed as plant pathogens include *Bemisia tabaci*, B. These insects transmit viruses under three genera: Begomovirus (Family Geminiviridae), Crinivirus and Closterovirus (Family Closteroviridae), and Carlavirus (not assigned to a specific genus) (Ciolakowska et al., 2021). These viruses are flying and is economically important, with fruits, tomatoes and cotton being the most affected crops (Hondelmann et al., 2020).

Because it plays a major role in the epidemic spread of numerous viruses, *B. tabaci*, the cotton whitefly, is the species that has been studied the most. This insect goes through four nymphal phases, all of which are marked by a strong attachment to the host plant, with the exception of a brief initial phase. They occasionally pierce plant tissues, settle in the spaces between cells, and feed on the sap of the plant in the phloem (Naveed et al., 2021).

The first larval stage itself is mobile, but it stays close to the plant. Active, flying adults give birth to multiple generations annually. Similar to the processes of transmission observed in aphids, begomoviruses are one of the most significant viral genera that are persistently transmitted by whiteflies (Ciolakowska et al., 2021).

These viruses have been found to have particles in the salivary glands and intestinal epithelial cells of insects. The symbionin protein is thought to be involved in the binding of viral particles to the insect's membranes. Nevertheless, studies have revealed that the capsid's incapacity to attach to this protein is not the reason why the Abutilon mosaic virus (AbMV) cannot spread, raising questions about the function of this protein in viral transmission (Naveed et al., 2021).

Several complex events have been observed in the transmission of this virus by whiteflies. For example tomato yellow leaf curl virus (TYLCV) persists as its vector longer than expected, even if it does not replicate in the insect (Ciolakowska et al., 2021). There is also evidence that TYLCV can be transmitted by eggs in infected males and

in females during mating. The viral capsid plays an important role in the insect acquisition, especially in the region between amino acids 129 and 134. Soybean chlorotic leaf virus (SCLV) has been shown to infect and infect a number of host tissues and life span and reproduction, indicating that the virus may replicate within the insect (Favara et al., 202).

Whiteflies also transmit many species of the genera Crinivirus and Closterovirus in a semi-persistent manner, with similar characteristics to those observed in aphid-virus interactions, where these viruses associate with the insect's foregut (Naveed et al., 2021). For example, the *Lettuce infectious yellows virus* (LIYV) remains in its vector for three days and encodes two capsid proteins: the large capsid protein (CP) or major protein, and the small capsid protein (CPm) or minor protein, the latter being essential for the virus's transmission by the insect. Meanwhile, *Lettuce chlorosis virus* (LCV) and *Cucurbit Yellow stunting disorder virus* (CYSDV) persist in their vectors for four and nine days, respectively (Favara et al., 2021).

4. Mealybugs

Mealybugs are piercing-sucking insects that feed on plant sap in the phloem (Figure 1). They are slow-moving compared to aphids and leafhoppers due to their lack of wings, relying on their legs and wind for movement and dispersal between plants (Ahmed et al., 2023). Mealybugs typically move from one plant to another by walking when plants are in close contact, with the nymphs being the most mobile stage crawling more actively than adults. Ants also play a significant role in carrying and transporting them between plants. Long-distance transport occurs via wind, making them less efficient virus vectors than the previously mentioned insects (Vercher et al., 2023).

Mealybugs are widespread globally and are also referred to as "false scale insects" because they lack scales. Several species of mealybugs have been recorded as vectors for economically important viruses, especially in tropical regions (Ahmed et al., 2023). These include viruses from the genus **Badnavirus** (family Caulimoviridae), several species from the genus **Closterovirus**

(family Closteroviridae), and the genus **Vitivirus** (not assigned to a specific family). The most notable viruses transmitted by mealybugs include (Abide et al., 2022):

- *Grapevine leafroll-associated virus 3* (GLRaV-3)
- *Lettuce chlorosis virus* (LCV)
- *Pineapple mealybug wilt-associated virus 1* (PMWaV-1)
- *Grapevine virus B* (GVB)
- *Grapevine virus A* (GVA)
- *Cacao swollen shoot virus* (CSSV), which is transmitted by six different species

For example, *Pseudococcus nijilansis* acquires CSSV within 20 minutes, with the insect requiring about 16 minutes to penetrate leaf tissues. The mealybug remains a carrier of the virus for approximately three hours, indicating a relationship that leans toward non-persistent transmission, with the virus likely being carried at the tip of the stylet (Ahmed et al., 2023).

PMWaV-1 is transmitted by the "pineapple pink mealybug" (*Dysmicoccus brevipes*) and the "pineapple gray mealybug" (*D. neobrevipes*), with the second and third larval stages being the most efficient in acquiring the virus, more so than other stages and even females. Given that GLRaV-3 remains in its vector, *Planococcus citri*, for nearly 24 hours, the relationship between the virus and its vector is likely semi-persistent (Abide et al., 2022).

Figure 1. Mealybug

5. Thrips

Thrips are insects with rasping-sucking mouthparts. Most species of thrips are polyphagous and can reproduce on a wide range of plants. The onion thrips (*Thrips tabaci*) is a globally widespread insect, feeding on approximately 140 species from 40 plant families (Carlos *et al.*,2022).

It is capable of parthenogenetic reproduction, with its larvae typically being inactive, while the adults are winged and highly active. Thrips feed by absorbing the contents of subepidermal cells. Their feeding behavior involves scraping the leaf epidermis with the upper mandible, which punctures the leaf surface, followed by the insertion of two maxillary stylets into the plant cell to extract the plant sap (Barbar *et al.*, 2022).

The viruses transmitted by thrips belong to the genus Tospovirus, family Bunyaviridae, which some species of thrips transmit in a persistent-propagative manner (Dhal *et al.*, 2021). Larvae are the only stage capable of acquiring these viruses, while adults are unable to do so. As larvae age, their efficiency in acquiring the virus decreases, but the adults that emerge from these larvae can carry the virus and transmit it throughout their lives (Ghosh *et al.*, 2021). The most effective time to acquire a virus is during the first instar nymph's feeding cycle, which takes about five minutes. However, depending on the plant species and vector, the inoculation period may last up to two hours (Barbar *et al.*, 2022). Temperature affects the length of the incubation period, which ranges from 84 hours at 27°C to 171 hours at 20°C. Males are more effective at transmitting the virus because of their feeding habits, even though females have a larger concentration of the virus (Carlos *et al.*, 2022).

The most effective vector for spreading Groundnut Ring Spot Virus (GRSV), Tomato Chlorotic Spot Virus (TCSV), Impatiens Necrotic Spot Virus (INSV), and Tomato Spotted Wilt Virus (TSWV) is the thrips *Frankliniella occidentalis*. Dark-colored strains of *F. schultzei* were found to transmit TSWV, TCSV, and GRSV with high efficiency, while

those with light-colored strains carried these viruses less efficiently (Zhang *et al.*, 2023).

When TSWV is repeatedly transferred from plant to plant without infection by thrips, this pathogen loses its vector capacity. There is a special relationship between thrips and viruses of the Tospovirus genus (Dhal *et al.*,2021). that the TSWV nucleocapsid accumulates in saliva, as well as in other tissues, and in disordered insect proteins in *F. occidentalis* larvae and adults. This accumulation occurs as the virus crosses multiple membranes of the vector through a "receptor-mediated mechanism." Evidence for this includes the fact that the insect only acquires the virus if the viral particle is fully enveloped, as this virus has external spikes made of two types of glycoproteins that protrude from the viral envelope(Zhang *et al.*,2023).. It is likely that these spikes serve as binding sites for a specific receptor located in the vector's midgut. Two proteins, with sizes of 50 and 94 kilodaltons respectively, have been isolated from the mentioned thrips (*F. occidentalis*). These proteins are associated with the viral glycoprotein TSWVG2. Their presence has been observed at several locations within the thrips' body, as the movement of the virus in the larvae was tracked using immunofluorescence staining techniques (Qi *et al.*,2021). The virus particles were first observed in the anterior midgut region approximately 24 hours after acquisition. The number of particles in this area increased, but they remained confined to the epithelial layer of that region for some time. In the late larval stage, the particles moved to the longitudinal and circular muscle tissues of the midgut and foregut. The salivary glands were first observed to be infected 72 hours after acquisition, as well as the ligaments connecting the midgut to the salivary glands. However, no viral particles were detected in the hemolymph or the basal lamina of the midgut(Tetty *et al.*,2023). This indicates that the virus does not reach the salivary glands via the hemolymph but rather through the ligaments connecting the anterior midgut to the salivary glands. This pathway differs from what is known about persistent viruses in other insects. Additionally, it was found that if the virus is acquired by thrips during the second larval stage,

it rarely infects the midgut, and therefore, the virus never reaches the salivary glands. Transmission of these viruses through thrips eggs has not been recorded (Qi *et al.*, 2021).

Certain species of thrips contribute to the indirect transmission of viruses belonging to the genera **Iarvirus**, **Sobemovirus**, and **Carmovirus**. These viruses are pollen-borne, and thrips carry the pollen grains and mechanically pollinate healthy plant flowers while feeding on them. However, there is no specific biological relationship between these viruses and thrips (Tetty *et al.*, 2023).

D. Transmission by Biting Insects

Several biting insects have been recorded as virus vectors in the orders Orthoptera and Dermaptera. However, the most important vectors are found in the order Coleoptera (beetles), particularly within the family Chrysomelidae, which includes plant-feeding beetles (Wendimu, 2023). Out of the many species in this family, only 30 have been recorded as vectors of plant viruses. In other beetle families, such as Curculionidae (weevils), Coccinellidae (ladybugs), and Meloidae (blister beetles), only a few species have been identified as virus vectors. Plant-feeding beetles do not have salivary glands. The beetles in the Chrysomelidae family feed on parenchymal tissues located between the vascular bundles, often leaving holes in the leaves or even completely damaging them under heavy feeding (Kumar & Kummar, 2023). These beetles also exhibit a behavior known as regurgitation, where they expel ingested food from their mouths. This process wets their mouthparts with the sap of the infected plant during feeding. It was previously believed that beetles transmitted viruses purely mechanically, but this has been proven incorrect for several reasons: (1) the failure of beetles to transmit stable viruses, such as the Tobacco Mosaic Virus (TMV); (2) some viruses transmitted by beetles remain in the bodies of their vectors for extended periods; and (3) there is a high degree of specialization between certain viruses and beetles (Wielkopolan *et al.*, 2021).

The viruses transmitted by beetles belong to the genera Tymovirus (family Tymoviridae), Comovirus (family Comoviridae), and Sobemovirus (which is not assigned to a specific family). These are stable viruses that exist in high concentrations within the tissues of their plant hosts (Kumar & Kummar, 2023). They have isometric particles with diameters ranging from 25 to 30 nanometers and are mechanically transmitted, with a relatively narrow host range and a limited number of vector species. Plant-feeding beetles vary in the time required to acquire these viruses; some can acquire the virus with the first bite, while others may need up to 48 hours of feeding to do so (Wendimu, 2023). The length of the acquisition time enhances the efficiency of virus transmission. The type of virus, the species of the vector, the host plant, and the environmental factors all affect how long the virus remains in the beetles. For instance, it has been discovered that, because cowpea plants have a higher concentration of the virus than soybean plants, the Cowpea Mosaic Virus (CPMV) retains longer in the beetle vectors when they feed on infected cowpea plants (Wielkopolan *et al.*, 2021). The plant fungus *Cerotoma ruficornis* was found to carry the Bean Rugose Mosaic Virus (BRMV) for nine days, while the plant fungus *Diabrotica balteata* carried it for only three days. The Bean Pod Mottle Virus (BPMV) was also detected to be carried by beetles that emerged from overwintering and were able to spread it after overwintering, which may indicate that the virus replicates within the beetle vectors. Some viruses are detected in the blood of insects soon after infection, and some individuals have been known to carry the virus after tested blood smears (Aldawood *et al.*, 2022). Evidence is generally lacking indicating seasonal incubation, except for Couch Grass Mosaic Virus (COMV), in which *Oulema* has been infected by beetle species. The evidence for this is the increased transmission rates observed 22 hours after acquisition and the failure of beetles to transmit the virus immediately after acquisition, with successful transmission beginning only after several days (Kumar & Kummar, 2023). It is believed that virus transmission by beetles is external, occurring via their mouthparts. The

regurgitation mechanism, where beetles expel virus-laden sap during feeding, is thought to be the primary reason beetles act as virus vectors. All viruses transmitted by beetles move through the xylem vessels, a characteristic that distinguishes these viruses from others, which are unable to move through such vessels. The mechanism of virus transmission by beetles remains unclear and requires further study due to its complexity and high level of specialization (Aldawood *et al.*, 2022).

Conclusion

In conclusion, this review article highlights the crucial role of insect vectors in the transmission of plant viruses, emphasizing the complex interactions between viruses, host plants, and insect vectors. The findings reveal that various insects, particularly aphids, whiteflies, mealybugs, and thrips, are significant in spreading numerous viral pathogens, which can severely impact agricultural productivity and food security. The article categorizes the modes of virus transmission and underscores the need for further research to understand these dynamics better and develop effective management strategies. Overall, the insights gained from this review are vital for enhancing agricultural practices and addressing the challenges posed by plant viruses in crop production.

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